

Modular programme for Education and Training

YOUTH SPORT COACH

M#4 Fundamental Movement Skills and Play

Declan O'Leary (Sport Ireland Coaching)
and the EduPASS Project Partners

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

TECHNICAL SHEET

Title: Modular programme for Education and Training: YOUTH SPORT COACH. M#4
Fundamental Movement Skills and Play

Authors: Declan O’Leary (Sport Ireland Coaching) and the EduPASS Project Partners

Number of pages: 19

Year: 2024

Cite as: O’Leary, D. & the EduPASS Project Partners (2024). Modular programme for Education and Training: YOUTH SPORT COACH. M#4 Fundamental Movement Skills and Play. EduPASS Project R#5 Project Output, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14711947>

Project: Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and Non-formal Settings

Project Coordinator: Claude Scheuer (until February 2023) and Andreas Bund (from February 2023)

Funder: European Commission

Programme: Erasmus+ Key Action 2: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices 2020

Action Type: Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education

Reference: 2021-2-LU01-KA220-HED-000051179

Timeline: 1 May 2022 – 31 October 2024

Project Sheet: <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/es/projects/search/details/2021-2-LU01-KA220-HED-000051179>

For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

PROJECT PARTNERS

The authors wish to acknowledge the contribution of the Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and Non-formal Settings (EduPASS) project team for the development of the outputs here referenced for EduPASS (2024).

No.	Institution	Involved researchers
1	University of Luxembourg	Andreas Bund
2	Universidad de Sevilla	Francis Ries, Jerónimo García Fernández
3	Sport Ireland Coaching	Declan O’Leary
4	Willibald Gebhardt Institute	Roland Naul, Sebastian Brueckner
5	CEREPS	Katharina Groene
6	Valgo	Manuel Valcarce, Sergio García

Disclaimer: The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use, which may be made of the information contained therein.

Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>

<p>2</p>	<p>Principles of Coaching Children</p>	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills and Play</p>	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Hands-on Coaching</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p>

		<p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Fundamental Movement Skills and Play
Module Number	4
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to achieve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation • Application of types of practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills • Use of coaching skills with a focus on explain, demonstrate, set up activity, observe, decision on intervention, communication and feedback, that is age appropriate
Module Description	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) and games skills (use of space, tracking objects, tracking others, creation of advantages, communication and working together) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in play activities.</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to access motor skills will guide this work.</p> <p>The Youth Sports Coach will learn to balance how each child develops their competence in motor skills, with the child’s knowledge/understanding of why & what they do, with the child’s confidence and motivation to be active.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours (including 8 hrs self-directed learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	<p>Class based and field-based presentations, during which coaches will be involved in experiencing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The types of practices and activities that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play. • Fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills • Applying practical coaching skills (plan, organize, observe, demonstrate, observe, communicate, provide feedback, evaluate), so as to contribute to the learning process for each child. • Self-directed learning as well as the completion of a coaching logbook / reflection journal will be used.

Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book			
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing Physical Literacy through Play: Coaching Children to Move Layout 1 (sportireland.ie) • Developing Physical Literacy through Play: Coaching Children to Think Layout 1 (sportireland.ie) • MOOC 2, Chapter 3 – How Children Grow and Develop Chapter-3-How-Children-Grow-and-Develop-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) – and associated videos, starting with iCK Course# 2 Ch3 How children grow and develop - Introduction - YouTube • MOOC 2, Chapter 4 – Motor Skills Development and Conditioning for Children COURSE 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy (icoachkids.org) – Download the study guide and see associated videos, starting with iCK Course #2 Ch4 Motor Skill Dev & Conditioning Intro (youtube.com) • MOOC 3, Chapter 2 – How Learning Happens and How Coaches Can Help Chapter-2-How-Learning-Happens-and-How-Coaches-Can-Help-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) and associated videos, starting with iCK Course #3 Ch2 Intro - How Learning Happens and How Coaches Can Help (youtube.com) • Move Well, Move Often Resources - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet 			
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes			
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 4.1: Understanding Motor Skill Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 4.2: Developing Balance, Coordination, Agility and Speed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 4.3: Developing Fundamental Motor Skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 1 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 4.4: Developing Game Skills and Play <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours 			
Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="464 1798 1393 2054"> <tr> <td data-bbox="464 1798 949 2054"> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • about children’s interests & preferences • of basic motor development • regarding group dynamics & social interaction </td> <td data-bbox="949 1798 1393 2054"> <p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to promote fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Conflict management skills • Cooperation skills </td> </tr> </table>		<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • about children’s interests & preferences • of basic motor development • regarding group dynamics & social interaction 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to promote fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Conflict management skills • Cooperation skills
<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • about children’s interests & preferences • of basic motor development • regarding group dynamics & social interaction 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to promote fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Conflict management skills • Cooperation skills 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • benefits of learner-centred approaches • basic pedagogical principles • pertaining to the role of play & exploration of activities in informal PAMPS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching / pedagogical skills • Motivational skills • Leadership skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Motivation • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty • Fun & enjoyment
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction • benefits of play & exploration of activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion • Honesty
Connection to other Core Module	Module 1: Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	

Course Structure

Course Title	Understanding Motor Skill Development		
Course Number	4.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation. Apply types of practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning of motor skills for children. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Motor Skills Development
	W / PE	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: Types of Practice leading to short-term and long-term learning
	SD	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the tasks in MOOC 2, Chapter 4
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mental Practice and Automatic stages of skill development Blocked, Variable and Random practice (short-term learning); and Deliberate practice and play (long-term learning) Short-term learning activities - Rapid Improvement, Not mentally demanding, Helpful for beginners / young, Confidence builder, Low retention / transfer, Quickly becomes boring and mindless Long-Term Learning Practice - Promote player's own thinking, Encourages retrieval of previous learning in a dynamic / realistic environment, High retention / transfer, Develops adaptable skills, Slow improvement, Mentally demanding / draining 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical application stages of skill development and types of practice Use of coaching skills of planning, organisation, explanation, demonstration and safe practice 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete the activities in MOOC 2, Chapter 4 – Motor Skills Development and Conditioning for Children COURSE 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy (icoachkids.org) – Download the study guide and see associated videos, starting with iCK Course #2 Ch4 Motor Skill Dev & Conditioning Intro (youtube.com) 	

Course Title	Developing Balance, Coordination, Agility and Speed		
Course Number	4.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand growth, development and maturation for children and its application to the development of balance, coordination and agility and speed (the fundamentals of movement). • Apply this knowledge in activities that emphasise the development of each of balance, coordination and agility and speed • Use of coaching skills of planning, organisation, explanation, demonstration and safe practice, and the development of observation and analysis skills to identify points of improvement in a child's competence. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Understanding Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Application in the development of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention in a child's competence for each of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed.
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balance - A state in which the body remains reasonably steady and stable. It's the foundation to safe, efficient and effective movement. Can be Static & Dynamic. Key points – Base of support, Centre of Gravity, Counterbalance, Core strength • Coordination – The skilful and balanced movement of the body and its parts at the same time. There are Internal (kinematics) and External (context – space/objects/others) parts. The aim is to produce an <u>action</u> or to produce force. Key points – From the head down, From the centre out, Mental organisation, Kinematic chain • Agility and Speed - Control of the body and its parts in a dynamic environment. Ability to move quickly and efficiently, including the ability to start, stop and change direction and speed whilst maintaining stability. Key parts – Start-stop efficiently, Change speed, Change direction, Change planes. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application in the development of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed. • Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning • Focus on all coaching skills, with an emphasis on observation analysis and the identification of point of improvement 	

	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention in a child’s competence for each of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed.• Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of each of balance, co-ordination and agility and speed. As an example use the resource - Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet
--	-------------	---

Course Title	Developing Fundamental Motor Skills		
Course Number	4.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand growth, development and maturation for children and its application to the development of fundamental motor skills. • Apply this knowledge in activities that emphasise the development of a range of fundamental motor skills, using the categories of Stability, Locomotion and Object Control. • Use of coaching skills of planning, organisation, explanation, demonstration and safe practice, and the further development of observation and analysis skills to identify points of improvement in a child's competence. • Add the focus of providing ipsative (person-referenced) feedback. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	1 h	Teaching Unit 1: Fundamental Motor Skills – Stability, Locomotion and Object Control
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Application in the development of Fundamental Motor Skills – Stability, Locomotion and Object Control
	SDL	1 h	Teaching Unit 3: Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention in a child's competence for a Fundamental Motor Skill, for one of each related to – Stability, Locomotion and Object Control
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills are combinations of the different fundamentals of movement: Balance, Coordination, Agility and Speed patterns. They can be categorised as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stability: Bending, spinning, rolling, twisting, reaching (Axial Movements), Starting/finishing positions (Static Balances), Different walks or transitions between positions (Dynamic Balances), Rtc. • Locomotion: Running in different directions / planes / Sliding / Gliding, Dodging / Jabbing, Jumping (height / distance) and landing, Hopping / Galloping / Skipping, Etc. • Object Control: Throwing/Passing, Catching, Cushioning, Kicking, Striking, Dribbling, Etc. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application in the development of a range of fundamental motor skills, using the categories of Stability, Locomotion and Object Control. • Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning. • Focus on all coaching skills, emphasising observation analysis, the identification of point of improvement, and providing ipsative feedback. 	

	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention (specifically ipastive feedback) in a child’s competence for each of a fundamental motor skill linked to Stability, Locomotion and Object Control.• Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of each of Stability, Locomotion and Object Control. As an example use the resource - Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet
--	-------------	---

Course Title	Developing Game Skills and Play		
Course Number	4.4		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand growth, development and maturation for children and its application to the development of game skills and play. • Apply this knowledge in activities that emphasise the development of game skills and using play. • Use of coaching skills of planning, organisation, explanation, demonstration, safe practice, observation and analysis skills to identify points of improvement in a child’s competence, providing ipsative (person-referenced) feedback. • Add the layer of questioning, listening and using secondary questioning in games skills and play situations, hearing the voice of the child and including them in game skill development and game design. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	1 h	Teaching Unit 1: Games Skills and Play
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Application in the development of games skills and play contexts
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICK and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Games skills can be listed as (not definitive): Use of Space, Tracking others, Tracking Objects, Communication, Support, Creation & use of Advantages, Anticipation & Countering, Dictating Pace, Keeping/Regaining Possession, Other • Play / Deliberate Practice / Play: Play can be defined as engage in activity for enjoyment and recreation. Coaches also use the concepts of Deliberate Practice / Play – which is practice / play with purpose or an aim. • Game Design: Children and young people can contribute to the development, adaptation and design of games to further develop game skills. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application in the development of a range of game skills, using play and deliberate play. • Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning. • Focus on all coaching skills, emphasising observation analysis, the identification of point of improvement, providing ipsative feedback and an emphasis on questioning, listening and the voice of the child, including them in game skill development and game design. 	

	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement, intervention and questioning and listening in a child's competence for game skills through play, and in game design.• Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of game skills through play and in game design. As an example use the resource - Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet
--	-------------	--